

Clay Membrane Electrode as a Tool for Cationic Activity Measurement in Solution

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Attempts have been made to prepare clay membrane electrodes suitable for measurement of cationic activities in solutions from some of the Indian clays. Padegaon soil clay (montmorillonite) membrane in its Ca-form performs best in comparison to the other clay membranes, e.g., Chinsura soil clay (montmorillonite), Contai soil clay (illite), etc. The membranes prepared from a kaolinite clay did not at all respond as an electrode. Padegaon soil clay contains free oxides, e.g., of iron and aluminium, but it is superior to 'pure' montmorillonite clay, e.g., aquagel, and also to a vermiculite having a higher b.e.c., so far as the performance of the membranes prepared from these clays is concerned. The removal of free oxides impairs the physical condition of the membranes, but their electrochemical performance is more or less maintained. Small additions of hydroxide sols of iron and aluminium to the cleaned clay suspensions improve neither the physical condition of the membranes prepared from them, nor their electrochemical performance. On the other hand, in some cases such membranes lose their responsiveness to electrochemical measurements.

The use of clay membrane electrodes for the measurements of cationic activity was first demonstrated by Marshall (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, 43, 1158), who also worked out the conditions and limitations of the measurements (*ibid.*, 1948, 52, 1284) and the interpretations of experimental data in the light of the existing theories of Teorell (*Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1935, 33, 282) and Meyer and Sievers (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1936, 19, 649). The experimental work has been extended to the measurements of activities of a large number of mono- and bivalent cations by Marshall *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), Mitra and Chatterjee (*J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1953, 1, 12), Bose (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 465) and Adhikari (*J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1957, 5, 198; *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1958, 21, 149). The action of the clay membranes as reversible electrodes being dependent on the exchangeability of the cations on the surface, a high base-exchange capacity is desirable, for which montmorillonite and beidellite clays have been mostly used. Since the cations differ in their exchangeability, often quite markedly, the ranges of their activity registered by membrane electrodes will certainly be different. In fact, the ranges of validity of the Nernst equation, attainment of equilibrium with outside ions, and other electrochemical performances of the same membranes vary appreciably with cations. About the use of different clay minerals as materials for membrane electrodes, very little is known. The studies by Mitra (D. Phil. thesis, Calcutta University, 1954) and Bose (*loc. cit.*) have shown that among others Padegaon clay, which is predominantly montmorillonitic and contains considerable amounts of free sesquioxides of iron and aluminium, performs quite satisfactorily as membrane electrode material. It is, however, not known whether these free oxides play any role in so far as the electrochemical behaviour of membrane electrodes is concerned. The object of the present paper is to investigate this aspect of the problem.

EXPERIMENTAL

Clay fractions ($<0.5\mu$) were isolated from Padegaon soil (montmorillonite), aquagel (montmorillonite), Chinsura soil clay (montmorillonite with a trace of kaolinite), Contai

soil clay (illite), Bagespura vermiculite (vermiculite), and Rajmahal kaolinite (kaolinite). The sesquioxides were removed from the clays following the procedure of Marshall and Jeffries (*Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1945, 10, 397). The original clays as well as the oxide-free samples were electro dialysed in order to prepare hydrogen clays; Ca-form and Na-form were prepared by treatment with requisite amounts of calcium oxide and NaOH. The clay membranes were prepared as usual by slow evaporation at 70-80° of 1.5-2% suspension under an infrared lamp. These were then cut into small discs and heated for 48 hours at 590-600°. Membranes were similarly prepared from 1 to 0.5 μ size fractions of Chinsura soil clay and Bagespura vermiculite, and also from the <2 μ fraction of Bagespura clay. The usual procedure of measuring the cation activities with membranes as prepared was followed (vide Mitra, *loc. cit.*).

The results of such measurements with membrane electrodes, prepared from different clays, are recorded in Table I-V, in which together with the range of applicability of Nernst equation, the electrical resistance, thickness, and composition of these membranes are shown.

DISCUSSION

The electrical resistances per mm of the membranes having the same cross section are small for those prepared from soil clays when compared with those from 'pure' clay minerals. Membranes prepared from the illitic clay from Contai soil possess comparatively low electrical resistance. Those containing relatively coarse fractions of clay are somewhat better for activity measurements. At the same time their electrical resistance is lowered and physical conditions remain unimpaired. The electrical resistance of the membranes depends on the cation saturating the clay and increases in the order: Ca-form < H-form < Na-form. The removal of free oxides from soil clays does not appreciably alter the electrical resistance, but makes the membranes prepared from them brittle. Moreover, the surface curls up on drying and often cracks, and hence it is difficult to bring them into suitable form for measurement.

Referring to Table I, the range of obedience to the Nernst equation is greater with the Padegaon Ca-form and aquagel Ca-or Na-form membranes for NH₄⁺ and K⁺ ions, the range of activities being 0.0001 to 0.01 for NH₄⁺ and 0.00011 to 0.243 for K⁺; with the other membranes the range of activities measureable is much less. For Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺, the range of activities, measureable within one tenth of a millivolt, is greatest with the Padegaon Ca- and Na-forms of membrane, the ranges being 0.00097 to 0.2367 for Na⁺, 0.0001 to 0.0243 for both Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺, and 0.0001 to 0.0081 for Ba²⁺. With the other membranes the measureable range is small.

In order to find out the influence, if any, of free oxides present in the soil clays on membrane performance, membranes were prepared from these soil clays after careful removal of free oxides according to the method of Marshall and Jeffries (*loc. cit.*). Unfortunately, however, the membranes of cleaned clays cracked and curled up on the surface on drying in the usual manner, viz., at 70-80°. Evaporation at 50-60° enabled us to get the membranes without much cracking and curling, but these were mechanically less strong than the original ones. The measurements made with some of these membranes, which are recorded in Table II, show that the oxide-free membranes have more or less maintained their electrochemical performance. The same remarks apply to the illitic Contai clay membranes, which were studied in a similar manner.

TABLE V

Materials of membrane.	Resistance per mm. thickness.	Thickness (mm).	Range of obedience to the Nernst equation.			
			$a_{NH_4^+}$.	a_{K^+} .	a_{Na^+} .	$a_{Ca^{2+}}$.
Chinsurah, oxide-free 0.5 μ size+5% Al sol.	870	0.27	0.0001-0.001	0.00011-0.00033	0.00097-0.00292	0.0001-0.0009
Chinsurah, oxide-free 1-0.5 μ size+5% Al sol	500	0.30	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Bagespura, oxide-free 0.5 μ size+5% Al sol	1550	0.20	0.00011-0.001	0.00011-0.001	0.00097-0.00292	0.0001-0.0009
Bagespura, oxide-free 1-0.5 μ size+5% Al sol	1580	0.25	Nil	"	"	0.0001-0.0003
Padegaon, oxide-free 0.5 μ size+5% Fe(OH) ₃ sol	960	0.24	0.00011-0.001	0.00011-0.027	0.00097-0.0789	0.0001-0.0081
Contai, oxide-free 0.5 μ size+5% Fe(OH) ₃ sol	500	0.22	"	0.00011-0.001	0.00097-0.0087	0.0001-0.0009
Aquagel+5% Fe(OH) ₃ sol	840	0.37	"	0.00011-0.027	"	0.0001-0.0081

Bagespura vermiculite has a high b.e.c. and membranes of good quality have been prepared out of it. Referring to Table III, it is to be seen that in comparison to the Padegaon clay membranes, the range of obedience to the Nernst equation shown by the vermiculite membranes, both in H- and Ca-forms, is smaller, being approximately 0.0001 to 0.001 for NH_4^+ , 0.00011 to 0.081 for K^+ , 0.00097 to 0.0263 for Na^+ , 0.0001 to 0.0009 for Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} , and 0.0001 to 0.00081 for Mg^{2+} . Taking these along with the results of the other montmorillonitic clay membranes, it might be said that a high exchange capacity of the material does not ensure better performance of the membranes prepared from them.

The effect of the size of the clay particle on the quality of the membranes can be seen from the data recorded in Table IV. Comparing these with the corresponding data in Table I, it is noticed that the performance of the membranes prepared from the larger size fractions of the clays does not improve, but in some cases, e.g., the Chinsura 1 to 0.05 μ fractions, the range of performance is lowered.

Removal of the oxides has been shown to impair the physical condition of the membranes, but their electrochemical performance is more or less maintained. Some experiments were also done in order to find out if addition of sesquioxides in colloidal form to the cleaned clay suspensions, prior to membrane preparations, improved the physical quality or otherwise influence the membrane performance. Table V shows some of the results which demonstrate that the presence of free oxides in the form of added impurities reduces the range of performance of otherwise good membranes. The membranes of the 1-0.5 μ size fractions, e.g., Chinsura (montmorillonite) and Bagespura (vermiculite), however, become altogether unresponsive as a result of addition of 5% by weight of an alumina sol.

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